

Survival of the Best Fit

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Keywords

AI Literacy, Algorithmic Bias, Business Ethics, Data Science, Discrimination, Ethical Decision-making, Human-Computer Interaction, Inclusion, Machine Learning, Media Literacy, Technology

Figure 1. Example visual from *Survival of the Best Fit*, illustrating biased hiring decisions and algorithmic discrimination (Gabor Csapo, Jihyun Kim, Miha Klasnic, Alia ElKattan). Used for educational review. Rights remain with the creators.

Introduction

Survival of the Best Fit is an educational digital game about hiring biases in artificial intelligence (see Figure 1). It was developed by an international group of former computer science students and published in 2019. The game aims to sensitize people to how AI mechanisms work and how easily incautious application can lead to misuse with drastic consequences. For example, as shown in the game, biased decision-making in hiring processes can result in discrimination against job candidates. By making hiring decisions, players provide data that is later used to train the game's hiring AI. Over time, problems arise that require the player to familiarize themselves with how machine learning works to understand the issues

and mistakes that were made. The game teaches responsible use of artificial intelligence in a simple, comprehensible way. The game is therefore well-suited as a starting point for digital literacy education for students in schools and universities.

Facts

Release date:	2019
Developer:	Gabor Csapo, Jihyun Kim, Miha Klasnic, Alia Elkattan
Game type:	Digital
Number of players:	Single player
Format:	Asynchronous
Time frame:	About 6 minutes
Languages:	English
Environment:	Computer or mobile device
Material:	None
Price:	Free of charge

Resonance & Criticism

In 2018, *Survival of the Best Fit* gained public attention when it was funded through a \$25,000 grant from "Mozilla's Creative Media Awards" (Gaylor, 2021). The game was further promoted in various tech publications, including *Medium* (Mozilla, 2021), *TechTalks* (Dickson, 2019), and *Quartz* (Edwards, 2022). The game has been criticized for offering an oversimplified, layperson's explanation of how AI bias takes shape. However, it communicates the fundamentals of machine learning in a comprehensible way to a vast audience (Dickson, 2019). The learning effects have not yet been scientifically investigated; however, the game uses mechanics such as 'delayed consequences' and 'guidance through questioning' that are considered valid and robust (Formosa, 2016; Joeckel et al., 2012).

Game Principle & Process

In the game, players become CEOs of a startup tasked with hiring new employees (orange and blue applicants) by manually reviewing applicants' CVs. Investors push players to increase hiring speed, which soon becomes difficult to manage. To address this, the game introduces machine learning to automate the hiring process. An AI algorithm analyzes previous hiring decisions to identify patterns in whom the player accepted or rejected and combines this data with hiring data from other companies. The AI then replicates the player's hiring patterns.

At first, the AI appears to solve the problem: hiring speeds up, and investors are satisfied. Over time, however, players receive complaints from highly qualified candidates who were rejected by the algorithm, putting the company at risk of a discrimination scandal. This forces players to examine the AI's decisions and identify the source of the error: because existing employees are mostly blue people, the algorithm learns to favor blue over orange applicants. To

encourage real-world transfer, the game ends with short explanatory texts that highlight how similar biases can occur in real life, such as AI systems prioritizing male hires over female ones. The game follows an experiential learning approach (Kolb, 1983). Players have concrete experience of hiring under time pressure, limited information, and delayed consequences, factors that can also occur in real life. Critical reflection is gradually prompted by skeptical in-game questions such as “A machine will think like me?” before the discrimination scandal finally makes it evident that something is wrong with the algorithm. The scandal shifts players' perspectives, allowing them to recognize the ethical implications they had forgotten while distracted by the goal of efficiency. Abstract conceptualization and transfer to new situations are fostered by a debriefing at the end that provides further examples for biases that occur in real life.

Learning Objectives & Educational Fields of Application

Through the game, players develop digital literacy in artificial intelligence by strengthening their critical thinking and ethical reasoning skills in this domain. Survival of the Best Fit provides a fundamental understanding of how AI works and improves players' ability to recognize and reflect on algorithmic biases. It creates awareness of how likely biases in AI are to occur and to go unnoticed by humans. It shows how algorithms work with feedback loops and can reproduce biases present in human decision-making.

Through time pressure and limited information, the game initially pushes players to make the mistake of trusting an AI without understanding how it works, and then highlights the hidden biases of automation by demonstrating its drastic consequences. In this way, the game ensures that players experience the dangers and likelihood of creating or falling prey to AI biases themselves.

The game itself is self-guided and takes only six minutes. Its short duration and simple mechanics make it easy to integrate into classrooms and workshops with minimal training. To improve and broaden reflection beyond the aspects addressed within the game (such as the real-world examples provided), it could be complemented by teacher-guided reflection and debriefing afterward.

Effectiveness

There has been no scientific investigation into the effectiveness of Survival of the Best Fit to date.

Potentially Problematic Aspects

Although the game addresses minority groups and their discrimination, which always carries the risk of reproducing stereotypes, it avoids this problem by symbolically representing different groups through neutral colors. However, the game is only available in English, and

its language is somewhat complex, assuming a certain level of education and digital literacy. Furthermore, the phone version has minor formatting errors that cause overlapping selection buttons, making it more challenging to play and understand the game. This problem does not occur in the computer version.

Reviewer(s): Saskia Sterzl, Zachary Fitz-Walter

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